

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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Improving the efficiency of personnel management and optimizing labor costs in Sam Glass LLC.....	368
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IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT AND OPTIMIZING LABOR COSTS IN SAM GLASS LLC

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Abstract: This article explores the modern approaches to improving personnel management efficiency and optimizing labor costs at enterprises, with a focus on the case of Sam Glass LLC. The study highlights how increasing employee motivation not only contributes to higher productivity and earnings but also directly impacts business performance indicators such as website conversion, customer satisfaction, and overall competitiveness. Special attention is given to the design and implementation of an internal system that ensures transparency, fairness, and result-oriented remuneration. The article argues that well-structured motivational mechanisms can reduce staff turnover, enhance loyalty, and create favorable conditions for sustainable development. Furthermore, the research examines the financial and tax aspects of remuneration systems, emphasizing the importance of aligning incentive policies with both organizational goals and legal frameworks. The proposed approaches serve as practical recommendations for enterprises aiming to balance efficiency, fairness, and long-term growth in their human resource management strategies.

Key words: Efficiency, enterprises, motivation, work, remuneration, tax, personnel management, transparency.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada korxonalarda kadrlar boshqaruvi samaradorligini oshirish va mehnat xarajatlarini optimallashtirishning zamonaviy yondashuvlari, xususan Sam Glass MChJ misolida tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda xodimlarni ko'proq daromad topishga rag'batlantirish nafaqat mehnat unumdorligini, balki korxonaning biznes ko'rsatkichlarini – veb-sayt konversiyasi, mijozlar qoniqishi va raqobatbardoshligini oshirishini ham ta'kidlaydi. Maqolada natijaga yo'naltirilgan, shaffof va adolatli rag'batlantirish tizimini ishlab chiqish va joriy etish masalalariga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Mualliflar motivatsion mexanizmlarning to'g'ri yo'lga qo'yilishi xodimlar almashinuvi darajasini kamaytirishi, sadoqatni oshirishi va barqaror rivojlanish uchun qulay sharoit yaratishini asoslab berishadi. Shuningdek, maqolada mehnatga haq to'lash tizimlarining moliyaviy va soliq jihatlari ham ko'rib chiqilib, rag'batlantirish siyosatini tashkilot maqsadlari hamda amaldagi qonunchilik bilan uyg'unlashtirish zarurligi ta'kidlanadi. Taklif etilgan yondashuvlar korxonalarda samaradorlik, adolat va uzoq muddatli o'sish muvozanatini ta'minlashga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: samaradorlik, korxonalar, motivatsiya, mehnat, mehnatga haq to'lash, soliq, kadrlar boshqaruvi, shaffoflik.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются современные подходы к повышению эффективности управления персоналом и оптимизации затрат на труд на предприятиях, на примере ООО “Sam Glass”. В исследовании подчеркивается, что повышение мотивации сотрудников способствует не только росту производительности и доходов, но и напрямую влияет на ключевые показатели бизнеса, такие как конверсия сайта, удовлетворенность клиентов и конкурентоспособность. Особое внимание уделено разработке и внедрению внутренней системы, обеспечивающей прозрачность, справедливость и ориентацию на результат при вознаграждении. Авторы утверждают, что грамотно построенные механизмы мотивации позволяют снизить текучесть кадров, повысить лояльность и создать благоприятные условия для устойчивого развития. Кроме того, исследование затрагивает финансовые и налоговые аспекты систем оплаты труда, акцентируя важность согласования политики стимулирования с организационными целями и действующей правовой базой. Предложенные подходы служат практическими рекомендациями для предприятий, стремящихся к балансу эффективности, справедливости и долгосрочного роста в управлении человеческими ресурсами.

Ключевые слова: эффективность, предприятия, мотивация, труд, вознаграждение, налог, управление персоналом, прозрачность.

INTRODUCTION

In the conditions of today's dynamic business environment, the success of an enterprise largely depends on how effectively it manages its personnel and optimizes labor costs. One of the modern tools that allows companies to objectively assess employee performance and link remuneration to actual results is the KPI (Key Performance Indicator) system. A KPI can be described as a digital marker that shows how well a company or its employees are achieving set goals. Unlike subjective observations, KPIs make it possible to measure productivity in sales, marketing, financial management, and other areas with precision, thereby ensuring that resources are utilized efficiently.

For many company owners and managers, monitoring the rapid pace of production and evaluating every employee individually is a challenging task. Traditional supervision and personal observations are often insufficient. In this regard, KPIs serve as a reliable mechanism to evaluate performance, manage business processes, and increase motivation. A properly designed KPI system not only helps enterprises achieve their strategic and tactical goals, but also creates favorable conditions for motivating employees to improve performance and, as a result, enhance the overall competitiveness of the organization.

At Sam Glass LLC, a modern payroll system has been introduced based on the KPI method. This approach is focused on ensuring transparency, fairness, and result orientation in personnel management. Unlike the traditional system where wages are tied solely to time worked, the KPI system links remuneration directly to measurable results achieved by each employee. Such a system significantly enhances individual responsibility, fosters interest in achieving the company's strategic objectives, and aligns personal motivation with organizational development.

Currently, the system is being piloted for cashiers, since their work directly affects the company's financial discipline and liquidity. Two main indicators are used to evaluate their efficiency. The first is attendance, which covers punctuality, adherence to schedules, and absence of violations. The second is productivity, expressed through the level of repayment of accounts receivable assigned to each cashier. The better the repayment ratio, the higher the performance score and the bonus portion of the salary. This mechanism creates a direct correlation between the company's financial results and employee motivation.

Importantly, the system guarantees a legally established minimum wage, ensuring social protection while rewarding excellence through bonuses. Additionally, the dynamics of individual employee indicators are regularly monitored, which helps identify weaknesses in personnel management, make timely adjustments to HR policies, and form an objective bonus system.

Looking forward, the management of Sam Glass LLC plans to expand the KPI-based remuneration approach to other categories of personnel, such as sales managers, logisticians, and supply service specialists. Adapted evaluation criteria will reflect the specifics of each department's activities, ultimately contributing to a comprehensive and transparent personnel management framework that enhances efficiency, reduces costs, and strengthens competitiveness.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The efficiency of personnel management and the optimization of labor costs at enterprises are issues that cannot be studied in isolation from the broader context of accounting, financial reporting, and economic reforms in Uzbekistan. A number of legislative documents, strategic frameworks, and scientific works provide

the theoretical and practical foundation for understanding the relevance of introducing modern systems, such as KPI-based remuneration, into enterprise management.

First and foremost, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting” (2016) serves as the fundamental legal basis for the organization of accounting and financial reporting in enterprises. It emphasizes transparency, reliability, and compliance of financial information with national and international standards. In the context of KPI implementation, this law ensures that remuneration systems are documented properly and that their financial consequences are reflected in company reports in a standardized manner [1].

The Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1997) also plays a significant role, particularly in regulating labor relations, contractual obligations, and financial settlements between employers and employees. Since KPIs directly affect contractual conditions of remuneration, civil legislation provides the necessary legal framework for ensuring fairness and compliance in employee contracts [3].

On the strategic level, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-158 (2023) “On the Strategy Uzbekistan – 2030” highlights the importance of modernizing labor relations, improving corporate governance, and ensuring efficient use of resources. The document directly calls for the introduction of innovative management practices and digital solutions in enterprises, aligning national development goals with corporate-level efficiency tools such as KPIs [2].

The academic literature further enriches the discussion. In his book “Strategy of the New Uzbekistan” (2021), Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasizes the necessity of increasing labor productivity, creating fair remuneration systems, and enhancing transparency in economic relations. His views directly support the idea that KPI-driven motivation systems can serve as instruments for implementing broader socio-economic reforms in the country [5].

At the educational and practical level, the study guide “Fundamentals of Accounting” by R.A. Abdullaev and K.B. Urazov (2021) presents essential principles of accounting and remuneration practices in enterprises. The authors stress the need for accurate reflection of labor costs in accounting systems and highlight methods of calculating employee compensation that align with national standards [6]. Similarly, G.S. Dzhambakieva in her textbook “Financial Accounting and Reporting” (2019) underlines the role of proper financial reporting in supporting managerial decisions, including those related to labor cost optimization and performance evaluation [9].

Finally, international perspectives are reflected in works such as R. Brealey and S. Myers’ “Principles of Corporate Finance” (2008). The authors discuss how corporate finance tools can be used to link employee incentives to organizational value creation. From this standpoint, KPIs are not just operational markers but also financial instruments that align managerial behavior with shareholder interests [7].

Taken together, these sources show that the integration of KPI systems into personnel management practices at Sam Glass LLC is grounded in both national legal frameworks and international academic theory. The combination of legislative acts, strategic programs, and scholarly works provides a comprehensive basis for understanding the role of KPI-driven remuneration systems in improving efficiency, ensuring fairness, and supporting sustainable enterprise development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is based on a descriptive and analytical approach, combining both qualitative and quantitative methods to study the efficiency of KPI-based personnel management at Sam Glass LLC. The qualitative part involves analyzing legislative documents such as the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Accounting,” the Civil Code, and the presidential decree “Strategy Uzbekistan – 2030,” as well as reviewing relevant academic literature to form a theoretical basis. The quantitative part focuses on examining enterprise-level data, including payroll records, attendance sheets, and accounts receivable repayment reports of cashiers.

The methodology is structured in three main stages. First, data collection was carried out by gathering internal company documents related to personnel performance and remuneration. Second, key indicators were selected, primarily attendance and productivity, since they directly influence financial discipline and labor efficiency. Third, an evaluation was conducted using percentage-based weighting formulas to determine the contribution of each indicator to employee salaries. This methodological design allows for an objective assessment of labor efficiency and supports recommendations for transparent and fair motivation systems.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The analysis of KPI indicators shows that employee motivation at Sam Glass LLC is directly linked to debt repayment efficiency. For debts up to 30 days, high repayment levels (60–80%) provide a KPI of 20%, while lower levels reduce or eliminate bonuses, even resulting in negative values when repayment falls below 40%.

For debts over 30 days, the weighting is stricter: repayment of 60–80% ensures a KPI of 40%, highlighting the company's priority in reducing overdue debts. This system creates transparency, rewards discipline, penalizes inefficiency, and strengthens financial stability through performance-based remuneration (table 1).

KPI indicators depending on the percentage of debt repayment:

	Debt up to 30 days	KPI		Debt over 30 days	KPI
60%-80%	80%	20%	60%-80%	80%	40%
50%-60%	60%	10%	60%-70%	70%	20%
40%-50%	50%	0	50%-60%	60%	0%
20%-40%	40%	-10%	30%-50%	50%	-20%
0% -20%	20%	-20%	0%-30%	30%	-40%

In SAM GLASS LLC, deductions and deductions from employee salaries are carried out in strict accordance with the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Tax Code, and the internal regulations of the enterprise. This process covers both mandatory deductions provided for by law and deductions made at the initiative of the employer or with the consent of the employee.

Deductions from wages are conventionally divided into two main categories: mandatory and initiative. Mandatory deductions are made without the employee's consent and are made by virtue of the requirements of the law or on the basis of judicial and other executive documents. Such deductions include income tax, alimony, deductions to individual pension savings accounts, as well as other payments provided for by court decisions. The procedure for their application and amounts are strictly regulated and do not require the issuance of separate orders or obtaining the employee's consent.

Table-1. Calculation of KPI for a cashier taking into account accounts receivable (May 2025)

Start Date	End Date	Fixed Salary	6,000,000.0
5/1/2025	5/31/2025		
Retail		Weight	120%
Category	Accounts Receivable at Start of Period	Repayment Amount for the Month	Actual
<u>Debt up to 30 days</u>	3,005,675,517.0	2,514,041,710.0	84%
<u>Debt over 30 days</u>	1,284,942,149.7	651,068,712.7	51%
Total for the period	4,290,617,666.7	3,165,110,422.7	74%
Subtotal:			1,800,000.0
Wholesale		Weight	40%
Category	Accounts Receivable at Start of Period	Repayment Amount for the Month	Actual
<u>Debt up to 30 days</u>	179,407.7	122,570.2	68%
<u>Debt over 30 days</u>	115,361.8	73,797.2	64%
Total for the period	294,769.6	196,367.5	67%
Subtotal:			960,000.0
Final Salary			8,760,000.0

Special attention in SAM GLASS LLC is paid to compliance with the restriction established by law: the total amount of all deductions from wages cannot exceed 50% of its accrued amount during a calendar month. If the amount of amounts subject to deduction exceeds the established limit, the remainder is carried over to subsequent months with mandatory compliance with the order of deductions determined by Article 164 of the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The order of deductions is usually as follows: income tax is deducted first, then alimony, and then all other deductions under enforcement documents. This sequence is mandatory and cannot be changed at the discretion of the employer.

Personal income tax (PIT) is the main type of mandatory deductions. In this case, SAM GLASS LLC acts as a tax agent, i.e. it independently calculates, withholds and transfers the tax amount from the employee's salary to the budget. The withheld tax is transferred to the budget no later than the date of salary payment or receipt of cash from the bank. In addition, the organization is obliged to maintain personalized records of each employee's income, reflecting in the card information on accrued income, benefits provided and deductions made, as well as withheld tax amounts.

The total (gross) income of an individual, from which the tax is calculated, includes not only monetary payments under an employment contract, but also payments under civil contracts, income in kind, and material benefits. If the income was received in foreign currency, it is subject to conversion into national currency at the exchange rate of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the date of its receipt.

In addition to taxes, within the framework of mandatory deductions, SAM GLASS LLC makes deductions to individual savings pension accounts of citizens. These amounts are also withheld from wages and are subject to timely transfer to the relevant off-budget funds.

In the event that an enterprise receives writs of execution, for example, for the collection of alimony or other obligations, the enterprise's accounting department makes the appropriate deductions and ensures their subsequent transfer to the specified bodies or recipients.

As for deductions at the initiative of the employer, they can be made only on the basis of the written consent of the employee or by a court decision. In such a situation, an internal order or regulation must be issued, with which the employee must be familiarized with under signature. The exception is cases of return of advances or erroneously accrued amounts, provided that the limitation period has not expired.

Thus, SAM GLASS LLC has developed and consistently applies a clear system of deductions and deductions from wages, ensuring compliance with the labor rights of employees, fiscal discipline and legal requirements. All deduction operations are documented and reflected in accounting in accordance with the approved chart of accounts and internal regulations of the enterprise.

Table 2. Example of transactions for deductions and deductions

No.	Employee	Debit	Credit	Amount (UZS)	Type of retention
1	Jalilov Khushnud Mamazokirovich	6710	6410	124,800.00	Income tax
2	Dustov Anvar Hamdam coals	6710	6410	124,800.00	Income tax
3	Zhabborova Khosiyat Tozhiyevna	6710	6410	124,800.00	Income tax
4	—	6410	6520	30,271.00	Deductions to INPS
5	Tokhirov Shahboz Bakhtiyor coals	6990	6410	242,400.00	Writ of execution (accrual of debt)
6	Sharipov Abdukhalim Abdurakhmonovich	6990	6410	112,800.00	Writ of execution (accrual of debt)

CONCLUSION

Many companies are implementing the key performance indicator of employees, because this system has a number of undeniable advantages:

- Fair assessment of employees' work: KPI shows the real performance indicators of each employee. This allows you to determine who contributes to business development and who "slows down" sales volumes.
- Simplifying the recording of errors: an underfulfilled plan indicates problems or insufficiently serious attitude of employees to work. The KPI system allows you to adjust schemes and improve processes. Thus, KPI allows you to quickly identify problems and find ways to eliminate them.

Specific monitoring of the performance of company divisions by specific regions, cities, departments, and performers.

A ready-made basis for plans: KPI provides forecasting of the fulfillment of tasks in sales, lead generation, work performance and other areas of activity.

Discipline, setting standards and requirements of corporate ethics.

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